

DAMAGE DETECTION OF COMPOSITES USING PULSED THERMOGRAPHY

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SUMMARY: Pulsed thermography is useful nondestructive evaluation (NDE) technique with fast, non-contact, single side, etc. It was introduced to ISTA/JAXA and has been applied to various composite specimens. Brief basis of pulsed thermography and these application examples are shown in this paper. The first example is stiffened CFRP panels with multiple layer delaminations by impacted load and the second example is compression after impact (CAI) specimens of FW-CFRP. These results are compared with conventional ultrasonic C-scan and they are agreed well. Pulsed thermography has demonstrated a significant advantage in NDE, especially in-service condition.

KEYWORDS: pulsed thermography, nondestructive evaluation, delamination.

INTRODUCTION

Three space-related organizations, NAL, ISAS and NASDA cooperated on a project for improving reliability of space vehicles just before they merged into one organization, JAXA on October 1, 2003. NAL, which is currently ISTA/JAXA, had been assigned to improve its NDE capability as one of the subject in it. A pulsed thermography was introduced and has been applied to NDE of some delamination damages in composite structures.

Infrared (IR) camera has been used for nondestructive evaluation but conventional IR camera is not enough capable of detecting delamination in laminate composites. Pulsed thermography is new technique [1] which combines instantaneous heating by flash lamp(s) and IR camera. It has features of fast and single side measurement with large area, and is good for detection of delamination in laminate composites. Recently, commercial product is available and it is very suitable for NDE for airplane or space vehicle in service. However the know-how for analyzing the data has not been established yet. Some of the successful results are discussed in this paper.

PULSED THERMOGRAPHY

Pulsed thermography, EchoTherm made by Thermal Wave Imaging, Inc., has been introduced for NDE of composites at ISTA/JAXA. This technique has a feature of fast, single side and non-contact with wide area. These features offer convenience for in-service and manufacturing applications. Fig. 1 shows a picture of pulsed thermography consisted of IR camera, cover box with two flash lamps, PC and power supply. It is a NDE device which can detect subsurface damage/defect by acquiring and analyzing temperature image on the object

surface after powerful flash. It can also detect density distribution in an sample or water in honeycomb structure. The principle of pulsed thermography is as follows.

1. The surface of the sample is heated with short pulse (< 5 msec) of a flash lamp array.
2. As thermal energy from the heated front surface diffuses toward the cooler interior of the sample, the front surface temperature of the sample falls. However, areas of the front surface located above subsurface defects (discontinuities in the material density, thermal conductivity or heat capacity) will cool at a different rate from defect-free areas.
3. The reduction speed in temperature becomes slow at the point that has lower thermal conductivity subsurface, such as delamination or void. The surface temperature appears temporarily hotter above the defect. On the other hand, the reduction speed in temperature becomes fast at the point that has higher thermal conductivity subsurface, such as water incursion in honeycomb sandwich panel.
4. An IR camera records the surface temperature for processing by a dedicated computer. In pulsed thermography, the thermal response of a sample to brief heat pulse is analyzed to create a subsurface image. Data acquisition typically begins before the flash occurs and continues for several seconds after the flash.

Furthermore, pulsed thermography has features of fast, wide area, non-contact, single side, and quantitative measurement. It is also easy to apply to curvature surface and to couple together divided images of wide area in the system. The measured data is a time-series of surface temperature distribution image that is mathematically improved signal to noise. A time-series of first and second derivative images of surface temperature can be calculated from this improved temperature images and these calculated images work for NDE. The typical schematic diagram of measurement principle and the photograph of the device are respectively shown in Fig. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1: Pulsed thermography, EchoTherm.

Fig. 2: Schematic diagram of measurement principle.

EXPERIMENTS

After the introducing of pulsed thermography at ISTA/JAXA, various composite specimens are evaluated with it. The successful results are described and discussed in this section.

Impact Damage in Stiffened CFRP Panel

A stiffened CFRP panel which was applied impact load from surface side with drop weight and then induced multiple layer delaminations was evaluated with pulsed thermography, and compared with ultrasonic C-scan [2]. Fig. 3 (A) and (B) show measured images of pulsed thermography and ultrasonic C-scan respectively. The pulsed thermography image does not only agree well with C-scan but pulsed thermography is much faster than C-scan. It is an advantage of this technique. It is also an advantage that pulsed thermography does not need any couplant. Therefore, it is suitable for NDE of the aircraft and spacecraft structures after production or in service.

Temperature image from lower left quarter of Fig. 3 (1) is shown in Fig. 4 (1) – (4) at the time indicated in the figures and time history of temperature at the point A ~ D are shown in Fig. 4 (5). The first derivative of temperature image from same data to Fig. 4 and time history of first derivative at the point A – D in Fig. 5 (1) is also shown in Fig. 5 (1) – (5). There are bonded stiffeners on the back side at the points A – C and is no stiffener at the point D.

The temperature plot of the point B breaks away from the other temperature plots in Fig. 4 (5) in early time. The points A and D have same break time but the different slope after the break point. The point C has almost a straight line. From these results and the position of the points A – D, the point A has no delamination in the skin and a delamination between the skin and the stiffener, the point B has a delamination in the skin, and the point C and D has no delamination. The only the difference between the point C and D is that C is a stiffened part and D is a skin only part. Subsurface delamination breaks away from the straight line at progressively later times, in proportion to their depth. These temperature plots help us to understand the subsurface defect but the temperature images Fig. 4 (1) – (4) is not clear enough to use for on-site inspection at airline but Fig. 5 shows delamination images clearer than Fig. 4 and this is useful tool for inspection. Second derivative of temperature image is also potentially useful.

In addition, pulsed thermography was used for NDE at the time of compression – compression fatigue test of an upper panel of main wing box. There were induced three delamination points by impact loads. These delaminations were evaluated if they would not propagate during the fatigue test. The specimen was evaluated before and after the fatigue test by ultrasonic C-scan. It was not realistic often to put off the specimen from a testing machine for C-scan because of the heavy weight of the end metallic fittings. That is why pulsed thermography was mainly used in this fatigue test for NDE when the fatigue loading was stopped. Fig. 6 shows one of the NDE results of impact delamination with pulsed thermography and ultrasonic C-scan before and after the fatigue test. These results show that there are no delamination propagations during the fatigue test.

Fig. 3: Evaluated results of stiffened CFRP panel.

(5) Temperature history at point A - D

Fig. 4: CFRP panel by Pulsed thermography.

(5) Temperature history at the point A - D

Fig. 5: Second derivative of pulsed thermography results of CFRP panel

Fig. 6: Ultrasonic C-scan and pulsed thermography evaluation results of CFRP panel before and after a fatigue test.

FW-CFRP Specimen

CAI test of FW-CFRP plates was conducted as a part of FW-CFRP tank study [2]. Delaminations of CAI specimens caused by impact were evaluated with pulsed thermography and compared with ultrasonic C-scan. They are agreed well and pulsed thermography is much faster. C-scan and pulsed thermography results with two different impact energy is shown in Fig. 7. In this study, FW-CFRP tank specimens were also made to establish safety standard of CFRP tank and these specimens were evaluated with pulsed thermography. One of these specimens has both artificial defects of delamination imitation and delamination caused by impact. The NDE results of this tank specimen with pulsed thermography are shown in the presentation.

CONCLUSION

A pulsed thermography was introduced to ISTA/JAXA and some of the successful results of this new NDE equipment are presented in this paper. As a result, it was clearly demonstrated features of pulsed thermography, fast, non contact and single side and dry couplant. It is also demonstrated that pulsed thermography is useful NDE equipment for in-service at airline and after the assembling at factory of composite structure, especially

detection of delamination. Pulsed thermography has shown high potentiality for NDE of composites.

1.7 J/mm		
6.7 J/mm		
	(1) Pulsed thermography	(2) Ultrasonic C-scan

Fig. 7: Nondestructive evaluation results of FW-CFRP CAI specimens.

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